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Manuscript ID:
MGT-2023-10035887

Volume: 10

Issue: 3

Month: January

Year: 2023

P-ISSN: 2321-4643

E-ISSN: 2581-9402

Received: 15.10.2022

Accepted: 05.12.2022

Published: 01.01.2023

Citation:

Abdul Rahuman, M. "A Comparative Study on Online Education and Traditional Education during Covid -19 with Special Reference to College Students in Tirunelveli." *Shanlax International Journal of Management*, vol. 10, no. 3, 2023, pp. 66–71.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.34293/management.v10i3.5887>

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“A Comparative Study on Online Education and Traditional Education during Covid -19 with Special Reference to College Students in Tirunelveli”

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Abstract

Education is important in our life. Without education, the commitment to life is very difficult. So everybody gives more importance to their education. The educationalist plays most important role in traditional education as well as online education. During Covid, 19-period lot of struggles were faced by our students. The concept of online education is entirely new to students. They meet some difficulties and benefits too. This paper shows the importance of education and aims to conduct a comparative analysis of student surveys between online live teaching and traditional offline teaching, to college students. The entire comparison of traditional and online education is analyzed deeply. Primary and secondary sources are used to collect the data. The primary source is collected through structured questionnaires from various college students. The secondary data was collected through journals, magazines, etc., and Various statistical tools have been adopted to extract the output.

Keywords: Traditional, Online Platform, Education, Impact, Methods, Quality

Introduction

Education is the key to success in our life. Education provides many opportunities in our daily life. Education also helps students with their higher education, plan to work in the future, learning knowledge, etc... Having an education in an area helps people think, feel, and behave in a way that contributes to their success and also improves their knowledge its not only for their satisfaction but also their community. In addition, education develops human personality, thoughts, and social skills. It also prepares people for life experiences. It makes people a special status in their society and everywhere they live.

A growing number of students are now choosing online classes. They find the traditional classroom modality restrictive, nonflexible, and not practical. In this age of technological development, schools can now offer effective classroom teaching through the Web. Highly educated people feel better our life it chances we get the move over good education polishes our mind, reinforces our thoughts, and also provide strengthens our character and behaviors toward others. Education equips us with more information in various field , particularly what we need to master in our job careers.

Traditional Education

The education system before starts through the Gurukula system. Students have learned education through the teacher's home only. But these opportunities are not getting to all students. After this British period Government introduced a new kind of education system. They established various schools and colleges. Students got education only from this institution they directly visited and learned their education. Its commonplace for teachers and students. After completing school education they continue their studies through college and universities. Various new education policies were implemented and modified the structure of education. This traditional were followed till now.

Online Education

In the early period of 2020, a global pandemic (covid- 19) broke out and severally affected the progress of education in various countries' universities and institutions, which promoted the progress of online courses at the same time. Computer-based instruction is shifting the instructive setting as an increasing number of students are seeking online education. Colleges and universities are now touting the efficiencies of Web-based education and are quickly implementing online classes to convene student needs worldwide. A different way of method was introduced and followed. It is entirely new for students in starting they feel some difficulties and benefits too. Students got to education through mobile and laptops. Internet access plays a major role in online education.

Modes of online learning

- Web-based Learning
- Webinars and Virtual Classrooms
- Video-based Learning
- Collaborative Learning
- Custom eLearning
- Mobile Learning
- Micro learning

Scope of this Study

In the early period of 2020, a global pandemic (covid- 19) broke out and severally affected the progress of education in various countries'

universities and institutions, which promoted the progress of online courses at the same time. A new method of teaching was introduced during the covid period it is called online education. A different kinds of method was introduced and followed. It is entirely new for students in starting they feel some difficulties and benefits too. Students got to education through mobile and laptops. Internet access plays a major role in online education.

Objective of the Study

This research work was carried out to achieve the following objectives are

- To analyze the factor that influences the preference of students for traditional and Online Education
- To identify the level of student satisfaction.
- To check out the knowledge and awareness level of the students about the different methods of education provided offline and online.
- To analyze the figure out what problems people have with faced both offline and online education.

Research Methodology

Research is defined as the important consideration of study regarding for a particular concern or a problem using various scientific methods. It is an efficient investigation into and study of resources and material to establish facts and reach new conclusions. Research is the art of methodical investigation. the advanced learner's dictionary of current English lays down the meaning of research as "a careful investigation or examination, especially through search for facts in any brands of information.

Area of the study

The data is collected only from the students studying in Tirunelveli city. Since the area of study is limited to Tirunelveli due to lack of time.

Sample Size

The number of sampling units selected from the population is called the size of the sampling. A sample of 80 respondents was obtained from this population.

Primary data

Primary data are in the form of “raw materials” to which arithmetic methods were applied for analysis and interpretation. The primary source is planning with random publics .data are collected through the questionnaire method.

Secondary data

Secondary data are in the form of the completed product as they have already been treated statistically in some form of the other. The secondary data mostly consists of data and information collected through various records, like. Internet websites magazines, journals, and books.

Table 1.1 Number of Hours spend in Traditional and Online Education

Particular	Traditional Education		Online Education	
	No. of Students	%	No. of Students	%
3 hours	14	17.5	48	60
5 Hours	18	22.5	12	15
Above 5 Hours	48	60	20	33.33
Total	80	100	80	100

Source: Primary data

The above table 1.1 shows the number of hours spends time in traditional and online education. Out of the 80 students, 60 percentage students learned education above 5 hours in traditional education and 60 percent of the students learned education online in 3 hours.

Table 1.2 Mode of Online Education

Mode of Online Classes	No. of Respondents	%
Google meet	41	51.25
Google classroom	27	33.75
What’s up	08	10
Microsoft team	04	5
Total	80	100

Source : Primary data

Table 1.2 shows the mode of online education. Out of the 80 students, 51.25 percent of students learned online education through Google meet

followed by Google classroom 33.75 percent, and What’s up 10 percent.

Table 1.3 Factors influencing Traditional Education

Factors	Weighted Garrett score	Weighted average Garrett score	Rank
Subjective factor	4824	60	I
Text book	3659	46	VI
Teachers	4607	58	II
Power point	4330	55	III
Interest	4325	54	IV
others	4038	50	V

Source: Primary data

The above table 1.3 shows that what are the factors influencing traditional classes. The subjective factor secured the first rank with the weighted average Garrett score of 60, Teachers secured the second rank with the weighted average Garrett score of 58, followed by power point interest of studies interest and others. Textbook secured VI rank with the weighted average garret score is 46.

Table 1.4 Factors influencing Online education

Factors	Weighted Garrett score	Weighted average Garrett Score	Rank
Subjective factor	4353	54	I
Text book	4254	53	II
teachers	4030	50	IV
Power point	4181	52	III
Interest	3736	47	V
others	3732	46	VI

Source : Primary data

The above Table 1.4 clearly shows that what are the factors influencing online classes. The subjective factor secured the first rank with the weighted average Garrett score of 54. Textbook secured the second rank with the weighted average Garrett score of 53, followed by power point teachers’ interest and others.

Table 1.5 Students Satisfaction Regarding Traditional Classes

Factors	Respondents Responses					Likert scale		
	SA	A	NI	DA	SDA	Weighted score	Total Score	%
Reduced cost	10	31	13	18	8	257	400	64.25
Convenience and flexibility	24	22	11	12	11	276	400	69
Increase time	8	31	8	25	8	243	400	60.75
Content update	16	26	19	11	8	271	400	67.75
Responsibility and priority	13	36	16	9	6	281	400	70.25

Source; Primary data

As per the above calculation responsibility and priority factor to students got 76.50 percentile points followed by convenience and flexibility.

Table 1.6 Students Satisfaction Regarding Online Class

Factors	Respondents responses					Likert scale		
	SA	A	NI	DA	SDA	Weighted Score	Total Score	Percentile Points
Reduced cost	12	34	14	16	4	274	400	68.5
Convenience and flexibility	18	35	9	10	8	285	400	71.25
Increase time	15	32	4	21	8	265	400	66.25
Content update	16	30	10	15	9	269	400	67.25
Responsibility and priority	15	31	11	16	7	271	400	67.75

Source ; Primary data

As per the above table convenience and flexibility got 71.25 percentile points followed by reduced cost 68.5 percentile points

Conclusion

Students are now very satisfied with the implementation of online live transmit courses in special periods, and also confirmed the role of online live-streaming courses in improving the excellence of teaching efficiency and appropriate use may help improve the teaching effect, but it is not possible to replace the teaching effect, but it is possible to replace traditional classrooms, teachers were inspired by this live- streaming lesson. They normally thought that online teaching was a form of teaching that was worth promoting. They planned to increase online teaching and use online and offline, class, and out-of-class teaching modes.

References

Agasisti, T., and Johnes, G. (2015). Efficiency, costs, rankings and heterogeneity: the case of US higher

education. *Stud. High. Educ.* 40, 60–82.
 Aguilera-Hermida, A. P. (2020). College students’ use and acceptance of emergency online learning due to COVID-19. *International Journal of Educational Research Open*, 1, 100011. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedro.2020.100011> Google Scholar PubMed Central
 Ary, E. J., and Brune, C. W. (2011). A comparison of student learning outcomes in traditional and online personal finance courses. *MERLOT J. Online Learn. Teach.* 7, 465–474.
 Atchley, W., Wingenbach, G., and Akers, C. (2013). Comparison of course completion and student performance through online and traditional courses. *Int. Rev. Res. Open Dist. Learn.* 14, 104–116. doi: 10.19173/irrodl.v14i4.1461
 Bao, W. (2020). COVID-19 and online teaching in higher education: A case study of Peking

- University. *Human Behavior and Emerging Technologies*, 2(2), 113–115. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hbe2.191> Google Scholar PubMed Central PubMed
- Bartley, S. J., and Golek, J. H. (2004). Evaluating the cost effectiveness of online and face-to-face instruction. *Educ. Technol. Soc.* 7, 167–175.
- BBC. (2019, June 19). What is India's caste system? <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-india-35650616>
- Bojović, Ž., Bojović, P. D., Vujošević, D., & Šuh, J. (2020). Education in times of crisis: Rapid transition to distance learning. *Computer Applications in Engineering Education*, 28(6), 1467–1489. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cae.22318> Google Scholar PubMed Central
- Beale, E. G., Tarwater, P. M., and Lee, V. H. (2014). A retrospective look at replacing face-to-face embryology instruction with online lectures in a human anatomy course. *Am. Assoc. Anat.* 7, 234–241. doi: 10.1002/ase.1396
- Bernard, R. M., Abrami, P. C., Borokhovski, E., Wade, C. A., Tamim, R. M., Surkesh, M. A., et al. (2009). A meta-analysis of three types of interaction treatments in distance education. *Rev. Educ. Res.* 79, 1243–1289. doi: 10.3102/0034654309333844
- Biel, R., and Brame, C. J. (2016). Traditional versus online biology courses: connecting course design and student learning in an online setting. *J. Microbiol. Biol. Educ.* 17, 417–422. doi: 10.1128/jmbe.v17i3.1157
- Bigelow, C. A. (2009). Comparing student performance in an online versus a face to face introductory turfgrass science course-a case study. *NACTA J.* 53, 1–7.
- Brazendale, K., Beets, M. W., Weaver, R. G., Pate, R. R., Turner-McGrievy, G. M., Kaczynski, A. T., Chandler, J. L., Bohnert, A., & von Hippel, P. T. (2017). Understanding differences between summer vs. school obesogenic behaviors of children: The structured days hypothesis. *International Journal of Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity*, 14(1), 100. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12966-017-0555-2>
- Chatterjee, I., & Chakraborty, P. (2020). Use of information communication technology by Medical Educators AMID COVID-19 pandemic and beyond. *Journal of Educational Technology Systems*, 49(3), 310–324. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0047239520966996>
- Columbaro, N. L., and Monaghan, C. H. (2009). Employer perceptions of online degrees: a literature review. *Online J. Dist. Learn. Administr.* 12.
- Daymont, T., and Blau, G. (2008). Student performance in online and traditional sections of an undergraduate management course. *J. Behav. Appl. Manag.* 9, 275–294.
- Dell, C. A., Low, C., and Wilker, J. F. (2010). Comparing student achievement in online and face-to-face class formats. *J. Online Learn. Teach. Long Beach* 6, 30–42.
- Driscoll, A., Jicha, K., Hunt, A. N., Tichavsky, L., and Thompson, G. (2012). Can online courses deliver in-class results? A comparison of student performance and satisfaction in an online versus a face-to-face introductory sociology course. *Am. Sociol. Assoc.* 40, 312–313. doi: 10.1177/0092055X12446624
- E., Shawnta, S., Green, A. L., and Hill, A. Y. (2006). A multi-semester comparison of student performance between multiple traditional and online sections of two management courses. *J. Behav. Appl. Manag.* 8, 66–81.
- Girard, J. P., Yerby, J., and Floyd, K. (2016). Knowledge retention in capstone experiences: an analysis of online and face-to-face courses. *Knowl. Manag. ELearn.* 8, 528–539. doi: 10.34105/j.kmel.2016.08.033
- Helms, J. L. (2014). Comparing student performance in online and face-to-face delivery modalities. *J. Asynchr. Learn. Netw.* 18, 1–14. doi: 10.24059/olj.v18i1.348
- Herman, T., and Banister, S. (2007). Face-to-face versus online coursework: a comparison of costs and learning outcomes. *Contemp. Issues Technol. Teach. Educ.* 7, 318–326.
- Kemp, N., and Grieve, R. (2014). Face-to-Face or face-to-screen? Undergraduates' opinions and test performance in classroom vs. online learning. *Front. Psychol.* 5:1278. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2014.01278
- Keramidas, C. G. (2012). Are undergraduate students ready for online learning? A comparison

- of online and face-to-face sections of a course. *Rural Special Educ. Q.* 31, 25–39. doi: 10.1177/875687051203100405
- Larson, D.K., and Sung, C. (2009). Comparing student performance: online versus blended versus face-to-face. *J. Asynchr. Learn. Netw.* 13, 31–42. doi: 10.24059/olj.v13i1.1675
- Lundberg, J., Castillo-Merino, D., and Dahmani, M. (2008). Do online students perform better than face-to-face students? Reflections and a short review of some Empirical Findings. *Rev. Univ. Soc. Conocim.* 5, 35–44. doi: 10.7238/rusc.v5i1.326

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